

Internship Program in Virtual and Modular Instruction as Perceived by Students

Ronnel V. Mancera

Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology Philippines

ABSTRACT: Virtual classrooms use a number of media forms to present information, catering to a wide range of student skills and learning styles. Videos, presentations, slide shares, animations, digital whiteboards, and webinars are all examples. A virtual classroom is an online teaching and learning environment in which teachers and students can present course materials, engage and interact with other virtual class participants, and collaborate in groups.

The study used descriptive quantitative research descriptive method. Descriptive survey is used to information or conditions with the use of questionnaire.

The study found that Through Online and Modular internship, students have acquired indeed knowledge and skills that can be utilized in their field. Though the overall interpretation wasn't that high enough, therefore, there is still a room to be improved in virtual internship. The existing challenges can be, first is the source of income, lack of gadgets to be used in the internship. However, these can be fixed in both helping hands. The Online respondents definitely encounter some challenges in a form of learning activities and learning patterns in which confusion is the concern, hence less is more. The brief the explanation, the more the students can under stance the process.

It is recommend that instructors may maintain their competencies on teaching students to throughout the internship of the students, hence they will be challenged to push themselves to learn and improve their performance despite of the challenges. Some challenges in a form of learning activities and learning patterns were major challenges yet the clarity of the activities would lessen the burdens to the students so that they can show their full potential. Thus, clarity is a must. The educators and instructors may understand the student's situation. It will help them to boost their self-confident so that they will not hold back to improve their performances.

KEYWORDS: Instructions, Intership, Modular on the job training ,Virtual classroom

INTRODUCTION

Virtual classrooms use a number of media forms to present information, catering to a wide range of student skills and learning styles. Videos, presentations, slide shares, animations, digital whiteboards, and webinars are all examples. A virtual classroom is an online teaching and learning environment in which teachers and students can present course materials, engage and interact with other virtual class participants, and collaborate in groups. We agree that the digital era has bloomed as schools and businesses have adapted to the change.

However, internet access in the Philippines is lacking. Apart from the need for increased speed, the majority of Filipinos cannot afford or use the internet. This means that students taking online classes must dress appropriately, either in a school uniform or in smart casual attire. There's also a challenge in choosing the best food during lunch breaks and behaving in public.

Course programs that required practical skills and competencies are found to be difficult in the absence of face-to-face interaction. The assessments of the acquired skills and practical application of knowledge are challenged since performance could not be observed during the actual presentation hence, On-the-job Hospitality Management Students were not able to report physically in an actual setting since face-to-face is not allowed for safety precautions. With that, this study aims to know how the OJT students perceive their learning experience thru modular instruction.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to know the challenges encountered dined to find out the perception of the NEUST Gabaldon students on the internship program in virtual and modular instruction.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions;

1. What is the socio demographic profile of the respondents of the third year HM students in terms of the following;
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 monthly income and;
 - 1.4 OJT Programs?
2. How may the respondents perceive the virtual and modular internship in terms of the following;
 - 2.1 challenges and difficulties;
 - 2.2 financial capacity and;
 - 2.3 learning activities and learning patterns?

Scope and Delimitation

The study is focused on the perception of the students on the internship program in Virtual and Modular Instruction.

Significance of the Study

This study is highly beneficial and significant to the following;

Students. Students will become aware on their strengths and weaknesses with regard to online and modular classes.

Parents. The result of study will be the basis for parents to monitor their child's during online or modular classes.

Teachers. This study will enable them to identify some challenges encountered in internship program in via virtual and modular instruction and can further enhance their skills in this new normal learning method.

Future Researcher. This study can be as basis for further research on internship programs in virtual and modular instruction.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design used is the quantitative research descriptive method. Descriptive survey is used to information or conditions with the use of questionnaire.

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

1. Socio Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The following data shows the socio-demographic profile of the respondents:

The following table presented the distribution and percentage of the respondents as to age.

ONLINE			MODULAR		
AGE			AGE		
19-22	2	20%	19-22	19	42.22%
23-26	6	60%	23-26	23	51.11%
27-30	2	20%	27-30	3	6.67%
Total	10	100%	Total	45	100%

Table 1.1 revealed that among the online students, the frequency of 6 or 60% of students between the ages of 19 and 22 came in first, followed by the frequency of 2 or 20% of students between the ages of 23 and 26 and the frequency of 2 or 20% of students between the ages of 27 and 30. However, for modular, the first rank were those aged 19 to 22 years, with a frequency of 23 or 51.11%, the second rank were those aged 23 to 26 years, with a frequency of 19 or 42.22%, and the third rank or last, with an age range of 27 to 30 years, with a frequency of 3 or 6.67%.

Based on the data presented above, the majority of the online students are ages ranging 19-22 years old which mostly students who rely to online for their internship program. Alongside, most students from Hospitality Management students in NEUST, Gabaldon Nueva Ecija who were in modular for their internship were also ages 19-21 years old.

SEX ONLINE			SEX MODULAR		
MALE	5	50%	MALE	17	37.78%
FEMALE	5	50%	EMALE	28	62.22%
Total	10	100%	Total	45	100%

Table 1.2 as shown in the table above, in the column of Online students rank first where equally distributed which frequency is 5 or 50% both male and female. While in the column of Modular students the rank first were female obtaining of 28 or 62.22% frequency and ranked second were male with the frequency of 17 or 37.78%

This finding shows that most of the respondents of online students were equal. However, in modular students the majority of the respondents were females based on the population of students of Hospitality Management students in NEUST, Gabaldon Nueva Ecija. This means most of the Hospitality management students who are utilizing modular were females.

Family monthly income revealed that among the students who are for online ranked first obtained the frequency 6 or 60% which monthly income ranges from 5,000-10,000 pesos. Followed by the frequency of 2 or 20% which monthly income ranges from 10,000-15,000 pesos. Third or last has the frequency of 2 or 20% which monthly ranges from 15,000-25,000. Both ranked as second obtaining 20%. However, for Modular, ranked first which monthly income ranges from 5,000-10,000 pesos with a frequency of 24 or 53.33%, second rank which monthly income ranges from 10,000-15,000 obtaining the frequency of 12 or 26.67%, and the third rank or last obtaining the frequency of 9 or 20.00% which allowance ranges from 15,000-25,000 pesos.

This finding shows that monthly or family income of each student or the respondents of both Online and Modular Students ranges from 5,000- 10,000 pesos. Second were both of Online and modular students' monthly income ranges from 10,000-15,000 pesos. Third and last, both online and modular students' monthly income ranges from 15,000-25,000 pesos. Hence, their family income will be divided into their family hierarchy of needs, and so as their wants.

OJT Programs revealed that all Online student which frequency of 10 or 100% were accustomed to take the PPA (Private Partner Agency) that is designed in the course they were taking. Likewise, to Modular modality which frequency is 45 or 100% were accustomed to take the in-house OJT (On the Job Training).

The finding shows that there is designated which are Private Partners Agency and in house OJT for the internship program that suits to the Hospitality Management Course.

Perception of Students in virtual and modular internship programs in terms of Level of knowledge and skill acquired (Virtual Internship) on the following statement: the instructor communicated politely and well with the students with a weighted mean of 4.50 and ranked as 1.5 together with the statement: Students have to adjust themselves according to the professional environment which also has 4.50 weighted mean: It is hard to make home laboratory for OJT students during new normal education system. with a weighted mean of 4.30 and rank as third: Well, explained possible work of students when they graduatee with a weighted mean of 4.00 together with the statement: The instructor had a better performance while teaching to his OJT students with 4.00 weighted mean and ranked as 4.5. The home laboratory done instructed by the instructor with 3.90 weighted mean and ranked as sixth: Virtual internship programs can help students to learn with a weighted mean of 3.80 and ranked as seventh: The instructor enhanced the skills of the student with a weighted mean of 3.60 and ranked as eighth: The virtual internship program has a big help to understand well the lesson with a weighted mean of 3.50 and ranked as ninth: A lot of skills students learn from the instructor with a weighted mean of 3.40 and ranked as tenth: The instructor teaches wisely to their students with a weighted mean of 3.10 and ranked as 11th or last. The total weighted mean in this particular category is 3.87 with an overall verbal interpretation of **Agree**.

The results show that the Online respondents have good assessment on Level of knowledge and skill acquired (Virtual Internship). Through Online internship, students have acquired indeed knowledge and skills that can be utilized in their field. Perhaps,

it is because they have been monitored by their instructors and they are well guided in their internship program. Though the overall interpretation wasn't that high enough, therefore, there is still a room to be improved in virtual internship.

Level of knowledge and skill acquired (Virtual Internship) It is hard to make home laboratory for OJT students during new normal education system with a weighted mean of 4.07 and ranked as first: Modular internship programs can help students to learn with a weighted of 3.98 and ranked as second: Modular internship programs can help students to learn with a weighted mean of 3.93 and rank as third: The instructor enhanced the skills of the student with a weighted mean of 3.91 and ranked as fourth: The instructor had a better performance while teaching to his OJT students with 3.84 weighted mean and ranked as fifth

The results show that the Level of knowledge and skill acquired (Virtual Internship) of the Modular students have a good assessment in which they have acquired the needed knowledge and skills through their modular internship. However, they are having hard time to make laboratory at home that is required in their program. Although the overall interpretation wasn't that high, therefore, there is still a room to be improved in either in this kind of internship.

Challenges encountered during the internship Lack of load for the student to join the virtual class with a weighted mean of 4.40 and ranked as first: Lack of financial capability to pay OJT fee for the internship obtaining weighted mean of 4.30 and ranked as second: Student's lack of source of income. with a weighted mean of 4.20 and rank as third: Parents' lack of financial support with a weighted mean of 4.10 and ranked as fourth: Lack of financial for ingredients in making home laboratory with 3.90 weighted mean and ranked as fifth

The results shows that the Online respondents encountered multiple challenges during their internship program. In which very particular to the first which is the lack of load in joining the virtual internship. Definitely this shows that students are facing a lot of struggles just to complete the virtual internship that will enhance and prepare them in the field. Overall, the interpretation will encourage the educators and instructors to be more empathetic to the student's situation.

Online students described the Challenges encountered during the internship in terms of learning activities and lining patterns: Unable to submit activities on time due to poor internet connection with a weighted mean of 4.10 and ranked as first: Not well understood what instructor teaches in virtual class, Not all modules are answered because don't understood properly the lesson, It's difficult to understand in virtual class because of noisy environment all three obtaining weighted mean of 4.00 and ranked as third: It's difficult to submit the activities due to poor internet connection with a weighted mean of 3.90 and rank as fifth

The results show that the Online respondents encountered some challenges in a form of learning activities and learning patterns in which it confused most of the respondents. As the first existing challenge is Unable to submit activities on time due to poor internet connection.

Modular students described the Challenges encountered during the internship in terms of learning activities and lining patterns: Not all modules are answered because don't understood properly the lesson with a weighted mean of 3.78 and ranked as first: Sometimes losing internet is one of the reasons why they can't join into the virtual class for having obtaining the same weighted mean of 3.67 and ranked as second: Unable to submit activities on time due to poor internet connection, and it's difficult to understand in virtual class because of noisy environment both obtaining weighted mean of 3.64 and ranked as third: It's hard to follow the modular class with a weighted mean of 3.58 and ranked as fifth.

The results show that the modular respondents encountered some challenges in a form of learning activities and learning patterns in which the first major challenge is not all modules are answered because don't understand properly the lesson. The clarity of the activities is a must so that students can answer it properly.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

1. Socio- Demographic profile of Respondent

Age –6 or 60% which aged ranges 19-22 years old and followed by the frequency of 2 or 20% which aged ranges 23-26 years old, and followed by the frequency of 2 or 20% which aged ranges 27-30 years old both ranked as second. From Modular students the ranked first were 19-22 years old with a frequency of 23 or 51.11%, second rank were 23-26 years old obtaining the frequency of 19 or 42.22%, and the third rank or last obtaining the frequency of 3 or 6.67% which aged ranges 27-30 years old.

Sex 5 or 50% both male and female. While in the column of Modular students the rank first were female obtaining of 28 or 62.22% frequency and ranked second were male with the frequency of 17 or 37.78%

Monthly Income 6 or 60% which monthly income ranges from 5,000-10,000 pesos. Followed by the frequency of 2 or 20% which monthly income ranges from 10,000-15,000 pesos. Third or last has the frequency of 2 or 20% which monthly ranges from 15,000-25,000. Both ranked as second obtaining 20%. From Modular, ranked first which monthly income ranges from 5,000-10,000 pesos with a frequency of 24 or 53.33%, second rank which monthly income ranges from 10,000-15,000 obtaining the frequency of 12 or 26.67%, and the third rank or last obtaining the frequency of 9 or 20.00% which allowance ranges from 15,000-25,000 pesos.

OJT Program 10 or 100% were Private Partner Agency. Also, to Modular modality which frequency is 45 or 100% which is On the Job Training.

2. Perception in virtual and modular internship programs

Level of knowledge and skill acquired (Virtual Internship) with an overall weighted mean of 4.50 and ranked as 1.5 together with the statement. For Modular the Level of knowledge and skill acquired (Virtual Internship) It is hard to make home laboratory for OJT students during new normal education system with a weighted mean of 4.07 and ranked as first

3. Challenges and difficulties experience during the internship

Financial For the Online students the challenges encountered during the internship in terms of financial on the following statement: Lack of load for the student to join the virtual class with a weighted mean of 4.40 and ranked as first. For the Modular students the challenges encountered during the internship is student lack source of income with a weighted mean of 3.5 and ranked as first.

Learning Activities and Learning Patterns For the Online students described the Challenges encountered during the internship in terms of learning activities and learning patterns: Unable to submit activities on time due to poor internet connection with a weighted mean of 4.10 and ranked as first. For the Modular students described the Challenges encountered during the internship in terms of learning activities and learning patterns: Not all modules are answered because don't understand properly the lesson with a weighted mean of 3.78 and ranked as first.

Conclusions

Through Online and Modular internship, students have acquired indeed knowledge and skills that can be utilized in their field. Though the overall interpretation wasn't that high enough, therefore, there is still a room to be improved in virtual internship. The existing challenges can be, first is the source of income, lack of gadgets to be used in the internship. However, these can be fixed in both helping hands. The Online respondents definitely encounter some challenges in a form of learning activities and learning patterns in which confusion is the concern, hence less is more. The brief the explanation, the more the students can understand the process.

RECOMMENDATION

Instructors may maintain their competencies on teaching students to throughout the internship of the students, hence they will be challenged to push themselves to learn and improve their performance despite of the challenges. Some challenges in a form of learning activities and learning patterns were major challenges yet the clarity of the activities would lessen the burdens to the students so that they can show their full potential. Thus, clarity is a must. The educators and instructors may understand the student's situation. It will help them to boost their self-confident so that they will not hold back to improve their performances.

REFERENCES

1. Agsari, S., Trajkovic, J., Rahmani, M., Zhang, W., Lo, R. C., & Sciortino, A. (2021). An observational study of engineering online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. PLoS ONE, 16(4), 25-41.
2. Baticulon, R. E., Sy, J. J., Alberto, N. R., Baron, M. B., Mabulay, R. E., Rizada, L. G., Tiu, C. J., Clarion,
3. Biggs, J., 2003. Teaching for quality learning at university: What the student does. 2nd ed. Buckingham: SRHE and Open University Press.

4. C. A., & Reyes, J. C. (2021). Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of Covid-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines. *Medical Science Educator*, 31, 615-626.
5. Chang, C. (2020). Teaching and Learning Geography in pandemic and post-pandemic realities. *Journal of Research and Didactics in Geography*, 2(9), 31-39.
6. Chaturvedi, K., Vishwakarma, D. K., & Sing, N. (2021). COVID-19 and its impact on education, social life and mental health of students: A survey. *Children and Youth Services Review* 121, 1-6.
7. Dost, S., Hossain, A., Shehab, M., Abdelwahed, A., & Al-Nusair, L. (2020). Perceptions of medical students towards online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic: a national cross-sectional survey of 2721 UK medical students. *BMJ OPEN*, 10, 10 pages
8. Calabrese, R. & Faiella, F., 2011. Theoretical and practical issues in designing a blended elearning course of English as a foreign language. In: G. Dettori & D. Persico, eds. *Fostering Self-regulated Learning through ICT*. Hershey, PA: IGI Global, pp. 162-178.
9. Chappelle, C. A., (1998) *Multimedia CALL: Lessons to be learned from research on instructed SLA*. *Language Learning & Technology*, 2(1), pp. 22-34.
10. Charmine (2021) "Coronavirus pandemic highlights failures of philippine education" -Barrot, Llenares and Del Rosario (2021) "Students Online Learning challenges during the pandemic"
11. Schleicher (2020) "Quality Education for all During Covid-19" Chaudrury (2020) "Challenges for quality education in the times of pandemic"
12. Sintema (2020) "Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on teaching and learning" Nothernor (2020) "Negative Impacts from the shift to online learning during the COVID-19 Crisis"